

**DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION OF A COLON-TARGETED DELAYED-
RELEASE MESALAMINE TABLET USING DUAL METHACRYLATE POLYMER
COATING: A GENERIC DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY FOR HIGH-VARIABILITY DRUG
PRODUCTS**

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ABSTRACT

Mesalamine (5-aminosalicylic acid) is the first-line therapy for the treatment of ulcerative colitis and mild-to-moderate Crohn's disease. However, successful therapy depends on precise delivery of the drug to the colon while preventing premature release in the upper gastrointestinal tract. Development of generic delayed-release (DR) Mesalamine formulations remains challenging due to the drug's high intrinsic pharmacokinetic variability, local site-specific action, and the critical influence of enteric coating characteristics on drug release behavior. The present study aimed to develop and optimize a colon-targeted delayed-release Mesalamine tablet through systematic core formulation and coating optimization. Core tablets containing 800 mg Mesalamine were prepared by wet granulation and evaluated against coat-removed reference listed drug (RLD) tablets to establish similarity in core release characteristics. Eight core formulations (F01–F08) were investigated, and formulation F08 demonstrated the closest dissolution similarity to the coat-removed RLD ($f_2 = 80.4$). Subsequently, enteric coating formulations comprising Eudragit® S100 and Eudragit® L100 were evaluated at coating build-ups ranging from 5.0% to 8.0% w/w. The optimized formulation (F013) containing a 6.5% coating build-up exhibited dissolution behavior comparable to the RLD, achieving an f_2 value of 75.1. The optimized formulation successfully prevented drug release in acid and pH 6.0 buffer stages while providing rapid and complete release in pH 7.2 phosphate buffer. Accelerated stability studies conducted at 40°C/75% RH for three months demonstrated acceptable assay, dissolution performance, moisture content, and impurity profiles without significant changes. The study demonstrates that a scientifically designed dual-polymer coating system combined with optimized core formulation can successfully overcome the formulation challenges associated with delayed-release Mesalamine products. The proposed development strategy provides a practical framework for future generic development of high-variability colon-targeted drug products.

KEYWORDS: Mesalamine, Delayed Release, Colon Targeting, Eudragit S100, Eudragit L100, Generic Development, Dissolution Similarity, Ulcerative Colitis.

INTRODUCTION

Modified-release (MR) oral dosage forms are designed to alter the timing, rate, or site of drug release in order to achieve therapeutic objectives that cannot be attained with conventional immediate-release formulations. MR systems improve therapeutic efficacy, reduce adverse effects, enhance patient compliance, and enable site-

specific drug delivery. Delayed-release (DR) dosage forms are particularly useful when drug release is required at a specific location within the gastrointestinal tract, such as the colon, to maximize local therapeutic action while minimizing systemic exposure.^[1-4]

Colon-targeted drug delivery has attracted considerable attention for the treatment of inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD), including ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease. Delivery of drugs directly to the colon allows higher local drug concentrations at the site of inflammation while reducing systemic side effects associated with premature drug release in the upper gastrointestinal tract. The colon also offers unique physiological advantages, including prolonged transit time, reduced digestive enzyme activity, and a relatively stable environment for local drug action.^[2-4,8]

Mesalamine (5-aminosalicylic acid, 5-ASA) is a widely used anti-inflammatory agent and remains the first-line treatment for mild-to-moderate ulcerative colitis and certain forms of Crohn's disease. The therapeutic activity of Mesalamine is primarily localized within the intestinal mucosa, where it inhibits cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase pathways, reduces the production of inflammatory mediators, and suppresses oxidative stress. Because Mesalamine acts locally rather than systemically, successful therapy depends on achieving precise drug delivery to the distal intestine and colon.^[5-11]

Several delayed-release Mesalamine products have been developed using pH-dependent polymer coating technologies. Enteric polymers such as methacrylic acid copolymers provide protection against drug release in the stomach and proximal intestine while allowing rapid release at elevated intestinal pH values. Among these polymers, Eudragit® L100 and Eudragit® S100 are widely employed because of their well-defined pH-dependent solubility characteristics. Eudragit® L100 dissolves at pH values above 6.0, whereas Eudragit® S100 dissolves at pH values above 7.0, making them particularly suitable for colon-targeted delivery systems.^[12]

Despite extensive clinical use of Mesalamine, development of generic delayed-release formulations remains challenging. Mesalamine exhibits high intrinsic pharmacokinetic variability due to its local mechanism of action, limited systemic absorption, physiological variability in gastrointestinal pH, and differences in gastrointestinal transit times among patients. Small changes in coating composition, coating thickness, or manufacturing parameters can significantly alter drug release characteristics and potentially affect product performance. Furthermore, coating process variables such as pan speed, spray rate, atomization conditions, coating efficiency, and film uniformity are known to influence the quality and reproducibility of enteric-coated dosage forms.^[12-17]

Therefore, the present study aimed to develop and optimize a colon-targeted delayed-release Mesalamine tablet using a dual-polymer coating system consisting of Eudragit® S100 and Eudragit® L100. A systematic formulation development approach involving core optimization, coating optimization, comparative dissolution assessment against a reference listed drug (RLD), and stability evaluation was employed to identify a robust formulation capable of achieving release characteristics comparable to the innovator product. The study further explores the impact of coating build-up and polymer behavior on delayed-release performance, providing a practical framework for the development of generic Mesalamine delayed-release formulations.

Drug profile

Mesalamine: Mesalamine is also known as 5-aminosalicylic acid or Mesalazine. Mesalamine is a aminosalicylate anti-inflammatory drug used to treat bowel disease, including Crohn's disease, colonic ulcers and inflamed anus or rectum.

Table 1.

Parameter	
Chemical name	5-Aminosalicylic acid (5-ASA)
Molecular formula	C ₇ H ₇ NO ₃
Molecular weight	153.14 g/mol
Appearance	White to slightly pink crystalline powder
Melting point	280–285°C (decomposes)
pKa values	pKa ≈ 2.3 (COOH), pKa ₂ ≈ 5.8 (phenolic OH)
Log P (octanol/water)	~0.7 (low lipophilicity)
Aqueous solubility	Slightly soluble in water; highly pH-dependent (↑ solubility in alkaline pH)
Solubility in organics	Practically insoluble in most organic solvents
Hygroscopicity	Low–moderate
Stability	Stable in acidic conditions; degrades in alkaline pH; sensitive to oxidation/light
BCS class	Class IV (low solubility & low permeability)
Intrinsic absorption variability	High intrinsic variability due to local colonic action and limited systemic uptake
Absorption	Minimal systemic absorption; primarily acts locally in colon
Bioavailability	Highly variable; approx. 20–30% (depends on formulation & site of release)
T _{max}	~1–4 hours (formulation dependent)
Half-life (t _{1/2})	0.5–1.5 hours (systemic), longer for acetylated metabolite
Metabolism	Extensively metabolized to N-acetyl-5-ASA (inactive) in intestinal mucosa & liver

Protein binding	Mesalamine: ~40%; N-acetyl-5-ASA: ~75–85%
Excretion	Renal (mainly as N-acetyl metabolite); minor fecal excretion of unchanged drug
Food Effect	Food may delay Tmax and increase colonic delivery; extent of absorption may decrease or remain unchanged depending on formulation. Generally, food slows release but improves local availability without significant systemic differences.

Materials

Mesalamine (API) was used as the primary therapeutic agent. Lactose monohydrate (Pharmatose 200 M) served as the diluent, while Povidone K30 (Kollidone 30) was employed as a binder during granulation. Purified water (q.s., %w/w) was used as the granulating fluid. Sodium starch glycolate functioned as the super disintegrant, Talc and Colloidal Silicon Dioxide were incorporated as glidants to improve flow properties of the blend. Magnesium stearate was used as a lubricant in the final blending step. All excipients were pharmaceutical grade and used as received without further modification.

Process Selection

Mesalamine is a high-dose active pharmaceutical ingredient that exhibits poor flowability and compressibility due to its cohesive nature and irregular particle characteristics. Preliminary evaluation of the API indicated unfavorable flow properties, as reflected by elevated compressibility index and Hausner ratio values. Such poor flow behavior can lead to inadequate die filling, weight variation, content non-uniformity, and inconsistent tablet quality during compression.

To overcome these challenges, wet granulation was selected as the manufacturing process for core tablet preparation. Wet granulation is widely employed for high-dose formulations with poor flow and compression characteristics, as it improves particle size distribution, bulk density, flowability, and compressibility. In addition, the process enhances content uniformity by promoting homogeneous distribution of the active pharmaceutical ingredient within the granule matrix.

Rapid Mixer Granulation (RMG) was selected as the granulation technique because it provides efficient mixing and controlled wet mass formation through the combined action of an impeller and chopper. The impeller facilitates uniform blending and distribution of the granulating fluid, while the chopper breaks agglomerates and promotes the formation of granules with consistent size and density. The resulting granules exhibit improved flow and compression characteristics, making them suitable for subsequent tablet compression.

Preparation of Core Tablets

Mesalamine core tablets were prepared by the wet granulation method using the formulations described in Table X. The composition of the formulations was designed based on information obtained from the reference listed drug (RLD), product information literature (PIL), and published literature reports. Lactose monohydrate was used as a diluent, Povidone K30 as a binder, and sodium starch glycolate as a

superdisintegrant. Talc and colloidal silicon dioxide were incorporated to improve flow properties, while magnesium stearate was used as a lubricant.

The prepared granules were evaluated for suitability prior to compression and subsequently compressed into capsule-shaped biconvex tablets using suitable tooling. Formulation variables, including binder concentration, disintegrant level, diluent quantity, and granulating fluid level, were systematically investigated to identify a core formulation exhibiting dissolution characteristics comparable to those of the coat-removed reference product.

Table 2: Formulations for core tablets of Mesalamine: (F01-F08).

Ingredients			F01	F02	F03	F04	F05	F06	F07	F08
S.No	Generic names	Brand names	mg/unit	mg/unit	mg/unit	mg/unit	mg/unit	mg/unit	mg/unit	mg/unit
1	Mesalamine	NA	800.0	800.0	800.0	800.0	800.0	800.0	800.0	800.0
2	Lactose Monohydrate	Pharmatose 200 M	132.0	132.0	198.0	198.0	198.0	198.0	179.0	189.0
3	Povidone K30	Kollidon 30	30.0	30.0	30.0	20.0	20.0	30.0	40.0	30.0
4	Purified water (%w/w)	q.s	22.0	22.0	22.0	22.0	22.0	18.0	18.0	22.0
5	Sodium starch glycolate	SSG type A	16.0	24.0	24.0	24.0	16.0	16.0	16.0	20.0
6	Talc	Luzenac Pharma	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
7	Colloidal silicon dioxide	Aerosil 200 Pharma	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
8	Magnesium Stearate	Ligamed MF-LV	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Total weight of core tablet (mg)			993.0	1001.0	1067.0	1057.0	1049.0	1059.0	1050.0	1076.0

Table 3: Granule and Tablet Evaluation Parameters of Mesalamine Core Formulations (F01–F08)

Mesh	Sieve analysis							
	Cumulative % retains							
	F01	F02	F03	F04	F05	F06	F07	F08
#30	11.2	13.9	15.9	12.2	13.5	10.9	13.1	16.7
#40	17.9	24.2	25.8	19.5	21.4	16.5	23.7	27.6
#60	32.7	46.8	44.8	34.1	38.1	30.2	45.7	45.0
#80	37.5	47.6	47.2	35.0	38.9	30.6	46.5	50.0
#100	52.2	75.3	64.7	53.7	56.3	48.0	70.6	65.0
Pan	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Bulk Density	0.49	0.52	0.5	0.502	0.44	0.49	0.49	0.55
Tapped Density	0.625	0.714	0.609	0.618	0.568	0.657	0.657	0.65
Hausner ratio	1.27	1.37	1.219	1.23	1.29	1.34	1.34	1.18
Compressibility index	21.56	27.08	18	19.4	22.53	25.49	25.49	15.38
Tablet weight (mg)	993.0	1001.0	1067.0	1057.0	1049.0	1059.0	1050.0	1076.0
Individual weigh (mg)	985-1000	995-1010	1050-1080	1050-1070	1045-1055	1055-1070	1042-1060	1071-1082
Thickness (mm)	6.45-6.48	6.45-6.50	6.65-6.75	6.62-6.72	6.58-6.65	6.60-6.73	6.59-6.68	6.69-6.82
Hardness	14.2-15.8	14.5-15.5	16.5-18.2	14.9-16.9	14.5-17.0	15.0-17.2	14.8-16.8	16.5-18.0
DT	4min 10sec	5min 10sec	5min 50sec	3min 30sec	3min 40sec	5min 30sec	10min 20sec	5min 10sec

Summary of Formulation Design and Optimization Strategy (F01–F08)

All formulations contained 800 mg of Mesalamine and were developed using a systematic approach to investigate the influence of critical excipients on granule characteristics, tablet manufacturability, and dissolution behavior. The formulation variables primarily included lactose monohydrate, Povidone K30, sodium starch glycolate, and granulating fluid level.

Lactose Monohydrate was varied to evaluate its impact on tablet weight, compressibility, porosity, and drug release characteristics. Lower concentrations were employed in formulations F01–F02, higher concentrations in F03–F06, and intermediate concentrations in F07–F08 to identify an optimal balance between tablet robustness and dissolution performance.

Povidone K30 was investigated as a critical binder to optimize granule strength and tablet integrity. Binder levels were adjusted to study their influence on granulation efficiency, compressibility, and dissolution behavior. Lower binder concentrations were expected to produce weaker granules with faster drug release, whereas higher concentrations could potentially retard dissolution due to increased granule density.

Sodium Starch Glycolate (SSG) was varied as a superdisintegrant to evaluate its effect on tablet hydration, disintegration, and drug release. Different concentrations were investigated to identify the level required to achieve rapid and reproducible release characteristics comparable to the reference product.

Granulating Fluid Level was adjusted to optimize wet mass consistency and granule formation. The influence of granulation liquid quantity on granule density, particle size distribution, and subsequent dissolution behavior was assessed during formulation development.

The formulation design was intended to establish the relationship between critical formulation variables and dissolution performance, thereby enabling selection of a core tablet composition exhibiting release characteristics comparable to those of the coat-removed reference listed drug.

Preparation of Core Tablets

Mesalamine core tablets were prepared by the wet granulation technique. Mesalamine was passed through a #20 mesh sieve, while lactose monohydrate and Povidone K30 were passed through a #40 mesh sieve prior to processing. The sifted materials were blended and granulated in a Rapid Mixer Granulator (RMG) using purified water as the granulating fluid.

The wet granules were dried in a fluidized-bed dryer until the desired moisture content was achieved. The dried granules were subsequently passed through a #20 mesh sieve. Oversized granules retained on the sieve were milled through a 1.5 mm screen and re-sieved to obtain a uniform granule size distribution.

For final blending, sodium starch glycolate and colloidal silicon dioxide were co-sifted through a #40 mesh sieve and blended with the dried granules in an octagonal blender for 10 minutes at 13 rpm. Magnesium stearate and talc, previously passed through a #60 mesh sieve, were then added and blended for an additional 5 minutes to achieve uniform lubrication.

The final lubricated blend was compressed into capsule-shaped biconvex tablets using suitable tooling. Compression parameters were adjusted to obtain tablets with acceptable physical characteristics and mechanical strength for subsequent coating studies.

Coating of Core Tablets

Enteric Coating Development

The delayed-release performance of Mesalamine tablets is primarily dependent on the functionality and integrity of the enteric coating system. Enteric coatings are designed to prevent drug release in the acidic environment of the stomach and permit drug release only after exposure to higher intestinal pH conditions. For colon-targeted Mesalamine delivery, the coating system must provide adequate resistance during gastric and small intestinal transit while enabling rapid drug release upon reaching the terminal ileum and colon.

Based on the dissolution results obtained from the coat-removed reference tablet comparison, formulation F08 was selected as the optimized core formulation for subsequent coating studies. The objective of coating optimization was to develop a pH-dependent coating system capable of producing a dissolution profile comparable to that of the reference listed drug (RLD).

A dual-polymer coating system comprising Eudragit® S100 and Eudragit® L100 was selected because of their complementary pH-dependent solubility characteristics. Eudragit® L100 dissolves at pH values above 6.0, whereas Eudragit® S100 dissolves at pH values above 7.0. The combination of these polymers was expected to provide effective protection in the upper gastrointestinal tract while ensuring drug release at colonic pH conditions.

Coating Procedure

The optimized Mesalamine core tablets (F08) were loaded into a perforated coating pan and subjected to dedusting and preheating at an inlet temperature of approximately 30°C. The coating dispersion was sprayed onto the rotating tablet bed under controlled process conditions until the target coating build-up was achieved.

Following completion of coating, the tablets were dried within the coating pan for approximately 5 minutes at an inlet temperature of 40°C to facilitate solvent evaporation and film curing. The coated tablets were subsequently cooled and collected for further evaluation.

The coating process parameters were carefully controlled throughout the study to ensure uniform coating application and reproducible delayed-release performance.

Table 4: Composition of the Core tablets.

S.No.	Ingredients	Brand names	mg/unit
1	Mesalamine	NA	800.0
2	Lactose Monohydrate	Pharmatose 200 M	189.0
3	Povidone K30	Kollidon 30	30.0
4	Purified water (% w/w)	q.s	22.0
5	Sodium starch glycolate A	SSG type A	20.0
6	Talc	Luzenac Pharma	5.0
7	Colloidal silicon dioxide	Aerosil 200 Pharma	5.0
8	Magnesium Stearate	Ligamed MF-LV	5.0
Total weight of core tablet (mg)			1076.0

Coating dispersion consists of 10% solids and the individual weights of each excipient per unit were shown in the following

Table 5: Composition of Enteric Coating Dispersion in Formulations F09–F013.

			F09	F010	F011	F012	F013
Coating dispersion with 10% solids			8.0% w/w	7.0% w/w	6.0% w/w	5.0% w/w	6.5% w/w
S.No.	Name of the ingredient	Technical grade	Qty/unit (mg)	Qty/unit (mg)	Qty/unit (mg)	Qty/unit (mg)	Qty/unit (mg)
1	Methacrylic acid copolymer type B	Eudragit S100	58.5	55.5	42.00	36.00	45.00
2	Methacrylic acid copolymer type A	Eudragit L100	3.09	NA	5.00	3.6	5.5
3	Dibutyl sebacate	Dibutyl sebacate NF	6.20	5.60	5.00	3.60	4.50
4	Talc	Luzenac Pharma	14.08	12.60	11.78	10.50	12.8
5	Ferric oxide Red	Sicovit Red	1.29	1.13	0.92	0.90	1.00
6	Ferric oxide Yellow	Sicovit Yellow	0.19	0.19	0.16	0.15	0.20
7	Isopropyl alcohol	Emplura	95 parts				
8	Purified water	NA	5 parts				
Total weight of solids for 10%w/w buildup (mg)			1159.35	1151.02	1140.86	1130.75	1145.00

To investigate the influence of coating thickness on delayed-release performance, coating trials were conducted at target coating build-ups of 5.0%, 6.0%, 6.5%, 7.0%, and 8.0% w/w. The relative composition of the coating formulation was maintained constant across all batches, and only the percentage weight gain was varied. Comparative dissolution studies were subsequently performed using the USP/OGD dissolution method to identify the coating level providing release characteristics most similar to those of the reference product.

Preparation of Coating Dispersion

A solvent system consisting of isopropyl alcohol and purified water (95:5, v/v) was prepared and divided into two portions in a 70:30 ratio. Eudragit® S100 was gradually added to the major portion of the solvent system under continuous stirring, followed by the addition of Eudragit® L100. The polymer solution was stirred at approximately 800 rpm for 30 minutes to ensure complete dissolution.

In a separate vessel, talc, dibutyl sebacate, ferric oxide red, and ferric oxide yellow were dispersed in the remaining portion of the solvent system and homogenized at 6000 rpm for 10 minutes to obtain a

uniform suspension. The pigment-plasticizer dispersion was then slowly added to the polymer solution under continuous stirring and mixed for an additional 15 minutes. The final coating dispersion was passed through a #100 mesh sieve to remove any undissolved particles and ensure uniformity prior to coating.

Process parameters of coating process

S. No.	Parameter	Results
1	Inlet temperature (°C)	30.2-35.0
2	Product temperature (°C)	22.9-25.6
3	Exhaust temperature (°C)	27.1-33.3
4	Pan rpm	15-30
5	Spray rate (g/min)	4.40-8.45
6	Atomization (bar)	0.5
7	Pattern air (bar)	0.5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparison of Test Core Tablets with Coat-Removed Reference Tablets

Establishment of Coat-Removed Reference Tablet Dissolution Profile

The reference listed drug (RLD) is a delayed-release Mesalamine tablet containing a functional enteric coating that governs the site and rate of drug release. Therefore, during formulation development it was important to

distinguish the contribution of the tablet core from that of the enteric coating to the overall dissolution behavior. Evaluation of the coat-removed reference tablet provided insight into the intrinsic release characteristics of the RLD core and served as a benchmark for optimization of the test core formulations.

To expose the core tablet without significantly altering its composition, the enteric coating of the RLD was carefully removed using acetone. Acetone was selected because Eudragit® S100, the primary coating polymer, is readily soluble in acetone, while the solvent evaporates rapidly and minimizes the risk of affecting the core tablet. The coating was removed by gently wiping the tablet surface with an acetone-moistened cotton swab,

followed by drying at 30°C for 10 minutes to ensure complete solvent removal.

Six coat-removed reference tablets were subjected to dissolution testing in pH 7.2 phosphate buffer using the optimized dissolution conditions. The resulting dissolution profile was compared with those of the uncoated test formulations (F01–F08) to identify a core composition exhibiting release characteristics similar to the reference core.

This approach enabled systematic optimization of the core formulation independent of the enteric coating and provided a scientifically justified basis for subsequent coating development studies.

Table 6: Dissolution profile of coat removed reference tablets vs. core tablets of test products F01, F02, F03 and F04.

Dissolution parameters	RLD	F01	F02	F03	F04	F05	F06	F07	F08	
pH 7.2 phosphate buffer, 900 mL, 50 rpm, paddle, 1.5 hr	Time (min)	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	
	values5	36.2	23.2	30.2	37.1	61.1	31.2	37.1	19.0	39.8
	10	66.4	49.6	56.5	61.9	77.8	58.6	63.2	31.6	67.3
	15	81.6	71.2	72.9	76.3	88.1	70.8	76.5	47.8	78.8
	20	88.1	83.9	80.3	81.9	91.8	78.2	84.1	59.5	85.3
	30	92.4	92.3	87.8	87.8	96.7	86.7	92.0	76.7	92.7
	45	97.3	98.1	94.1	93.1	99.7	95.1	97.1	89.0	98.3
	60	98.1	99.2	96.9	95.0	101.0	95.8	99.3	98.6	99.9
	f2		50.3	57.2	66.4	46.4	56	75.7	30.0	80.4

Graphical representation

Figure 1: Comparative dissolution profiles of coat removed reference tablet Vs. uncoated test tablets in pH 7.2 phosphate buffer.

Observation: All formulations showed a time-dependent increase in drug release; however, clear differences were observed in the initial and intermediate time points.

At 5 minutes, F08 and F06 exhibited drug release very close to that of the RLD, indicating comparable initial release behavior. All formulations achieved

approximately $\geq 90\%$ drug release, matching the RLD and confirming comparable extent of release at the final stage.

Overall, among all evaluated formulations, F08 exhibited the most consistent and closest similarity to the RLD across initial, intermediate, and final time points. The

release pattern of F08 closely mirrors that of the reference product without showing excessively rapid or delayed release, making F08 the most promising formulation for further development.

Conclusion: Although both F06 and F08 demonstrated dissolution profiles similar to that of the coat-removed reference tablet, formulation F08 exhibited superior overall profile matching across early, intermediate, and final sampling time points. Furthermore, F08 provided a balanced composition with respect to binder concentration, disintegrant level, and diluent content, resulting in more consistent release behavior. Therefore,

F08 was selected as the optimized core formulation for subsequent coating optimization studies.

In-vitro evaluation of the coated tablets: Mesalamine DR Tablets are official in USP. The OGD dissolution test is used as surrogate in the development and screening of formulations.

- I. USP apparatus II at 100 rpm, 2 hrs in 500 mL of 0.1 N HCL followed by
- II. USP apparatus II at 100 rpm, 1 hr in 900 mL of pH 6.0 phosphate buffer followed by
- III. USP apparatus II at 50 rpm, 1.5 hrs in 900 mL of pH 7.2 phosphate buffer.

Table 7: Reference Drug Product as per USP monographs Dissolution Methods.

Stage	Acid stage	Buffer stage 1	Buffer stage 2
Apparatus	USP II (Paddle)	USP II (Paddle)	USP II (Paddle)
Media	0.1N HCl	pH6.0 Phosphate buffer	pH 7.2 Phosphate buffer
RPM	100	100	50
Volume	500 mL	900 mL	900 mL
Recommended time points	2 hrs	1 hr	1.5 hr
Specification limit	No individual value exceeds 1% dissolved in 2Hrs.	No individual value exceeds 1% dissolved in 1Hr.	Q=80% at 1.5 hrs

Dissolution study performed on 6 units of finished product (both RLD and Test product). Initially tablets dropped into Acid medium followed by Buffer stage 1 followed by Buffer stage 2 at above specified conditions.

Based on the results it was observed that release in first two media i.e., Acid stage and Buffer stage 1 is less than 1.0% which is within the limits. Drug release mainly observed in Buffer stage 2 i.e., pH 7.2 phosphate buffer.

Table 8: Comparative dissolution profile of Reference tablet Vs. Test formulations

Coating buildup		RLD	F09	F10	F11	F12	F13
0.1 N HCl, 500ml, Paddle and 100RPM			8%	7%	6%	5%	6.5%
NMT 1%	Time(hr)	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel
	2h	0.2	0	0	0	0	0
6.0 Phosphate buffer, 900ml, Paddle and 100 RPM	Time(hr)	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel
	1h	0.4	0	0	0	0	0
7.2 pH phosphate buffer, 900ml, Paddle, 50 RPM	Time (min)	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel	%Rel
	5	4.0	0.8	3.2	1.2	1.0	2.8
	10	7.3	3.2	6.3	3.0	5.0	5.5
	15	12.5	6.8	6.5	9.0	7.1	8.8
	30	55.3	27.4	21.5	61.7	74.1	51.6
	45	83.0	55.8	60	93.2	95.7	86.6
	60	93.2	76.4	82.0	99.3	101.8	96.1
	75	100.7	97.0	104.6	102.9	102.3	100.1
90	102.6	100.8	100.2	102.1	102.3	100.8	
F2			39.3	39.4	60.6	49.3	75.1

The coating optimization study established a narrow design space for delayed-release Mesalamine tablets. Both insufficient and excessive coating levels adversely affected dissolution similarity relative to the reference product. Formulations containing 7.0% and 8.0% coating build-up exhibited delayed drug release due to increased film thickness, whereas the 5.0% coating level resulted

in premature drug release. The highest dissolution similarity was achieved at a coating build-up of 6.5% (f2 = 75.1), indicating that this coating level provides an optimal balance between enteric protection and rapid release under colonic pH conditions. These findings highlight the critical influence of coating thickness on the performance of pH-dependent drug delivery systems.

Graphical representation

Figure 2.

OBSERVATION

The coating build-up significantly influenced the dissolution behavior of Mesalamine delayed-release tablets. Formulations with higher coating levels (F09 and F10) exhibited slower drug release due to increased film thickness, which delayed media penetration and polymer dissolution. In contrast, formulation F12 containing a 5.0% coating build-up showed faster drug release, indicating insufficient coating thickness to maintain the desired lag time. The optimized formulation F013 (6.5% build-up) demonstrated a dissolution profile most comparable to the RLD ($f_2 = 75.1$), providing an optimal

balance between enteric protection and rapid drug release at colonic pH conditions.

Dissolution profile comparison between test and reference formulations was performed using the similarity factor (f_2). According to regulatory guidance, f_2 values between 50 and 100 indicate similarity between two dissolution profiles. For the discriminatory dissolution studies, the observed f_2 values were additionally compared with the corresponding 5th percentile limits specified in the Product-Specific Guidance (PSG) for Mesalamine delayed-release tablets data presented below.

Table 9: Comparative dissolution in Acid → pH 6.5 phosphate buffer of Test vs Reference product.

Batch No.		Asacol HD		F013	
No. Of units		12 units		12 units	
Dissolution media ↓	Time	% Release	% RSD	% Release	% RSD
0.1N HCL, 500mL, Paddle, 100RPM	2 Hrs	0.0	#DIV/0!	0.0	233.5
	10	0.0	#DIV/0!	0.0	233.5
	20	0.0	346.4	0.0	233.5
	30	0.0	#DIV/0!	0.2	196.3
	45	0.0	#DIV/0!	0.0	233.5
	60	0.3	211.1	0.0	#DIV/0!
	75	0.7	297.1	0.1	154.5
	90	1.5	333.8	0.0	#DIV/0!
	120	4.6	256.7	0.1	166.8
	150	9.6	182.3	0.5	81.2
	180	13.0	171.6	5.7	74.9
	240	21.4	140.9	31.1	29.9
	300	32.2	121.7	42.3	14.0
	360	36.0	104.0	54.6	12.9
Observed F2				51.6	
5% percentile		-		42	

Table 10: Comparative dissolution in Acid→pH 6.8 phosphate buffer of Test vs Reference product.

Batch No.		Asacol HD		F013	
No. Of units		12 units		6 units	
Dissolution media↓	Time	% Release	% RSD	% Release	% RSD
0.1N HCL, 500mL,Paddle, 100RPM	2 Hrs	0.0	346.4	0.0	#DIV/0!
pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, 900 mL, 50 rpm, paddle, 1.5 hr	10	0.2	75.8	0.5	83.6
	20	0.2	78.3	0.1	120.3
	30	0.3	58.3	0.3	95.7
	45	0.2	150.2	0.2	77.8
	60	2.9	229.9	0.2	73.9
	75	8.3	161.8	4.1	5.0
	90	19.2	100.4	11.1	18.4
	120	42.3	76.0	21.6	76.0
	150	53.8	71.6	66.0	12.7
	180	63.8	55.1	75.0	12.5
	240	84.3	15.7	80.4	11.5
	300	89.0	10.7	93.8	3.8
	360	93.9	8.2	98.8	3.4
Observed F2				54	
5% percentile		-		43	

Table 11: Comparative dissolution in Acid→pH 7.2 phosphate buffer of Test vs Reference product.

Batch No.		Asacol HD		F013	
No. Of units		12 units		6 units	
Dissolution media↓	Time	% Release	% RSD	% Release	% RSD
0.1N HCL, 500mL, Paddle, 100RPM	2 Hrs	0.1	127.0	0.0	#DIV/0!
pH 7.2 phosphate buffer, 900 mL, 50 rpm, paddle, 1.5 hr	10	0.1	140.8	0.5	33.5
	20	0.4	274.1	0.3	36.9
	30	3.4	180.3	0.7	82.5
	45	36.9	57.5	19.2	37.8
	60	74.5	17.5	78.1	10.7
	75	87.0	9.7	89.7	4.1
	90	92.6	5.8	97.0	3.3
	120	96.4	2.5	100.9	2.4
	150	97.1	2.3	100.9	2.1
	180	97.6	1.6	101.4	1.1
	240	98.2	1.7	101.8	1.9
	300	97.8	1.7	100.9	1.6
	360	97.3	1.7	102.2	1.3
Observed f2				58	
5% percentile		-		49	

Table 12: Comparative dissolution in Acid→pH 7.5 phosphate buffer of Test vs Reference product.

Batch No.		Asacol HD		F013	
No. Of units		12 units		12 units	
Dissolution media↓	Time	% Release	% RSD	% Release	% RSD
0.1N HCL, 500mL, Paddle, 100RPM	2 Hrs	0.1	199.6	0.0	#DIV/0!
pH 7.5 phosphate buffer, 900 mL, 50 rpm, paddle, 1.5 hr	10	0.1	143.1	0.0	#DIV/0!
	20	3.1	175.3	6.6	65.5
	30	38.4	48.5	52.0	29.2
	45	82.7	6.7	86.4	4.9
	60	93.4	3.0	93.1	2.0
	75	97.4	1.9	97.1	1.1
	90	98.3	1.7	98.5	0.8
	120	99.2	1.5	98.7	1.7
	150	99.7	1.1	99.7	0.5
	180	99.7	1.3	99.6	1.0
	240	100.6	1.4	100.8	0.7

	300	101.1	1.5	103.4	0.7
	360	101.9	1.7	103.9	1.2
Observed f2					59
5% percentile					47

Dissolution data summary table

Dissolution Condition	Observed f2	5 Percentile	Interpretation
USP Method (pH 6.0 → 7.2)	75	55	Similar
pH 6.5	51.6	42	Similar
pH 6.8	54	43	Similar
pH 7.2	58	49	Similar
pH 7.5	59	47	Similar

OBSERVATION

The discriminatory dissolution studies demonstrated that the optimized formulation exhibited pH-dependent drug release behavior comparable to the reference product across all evaluated conditions. Both formulations maintained effective enteric protection during the acid stage, with negligible drug release observed under gastric conditions. At pH 6.5, drug release was limited and gradual, while increasing buffer pH resulted in

progressively faster dissolution profiles. Rapid and nearly complete drug release was observed at pH 7.2 and 7.5, reflecting the ionization behavior of the enteric coating polymers. The observed f2 values exceeded the corresponding 5th percentile acceptance criteria at all evaluated pH conditions, confirming dissolution similarity and demonstrating the robustness of the optimized Eudragit® L100/Eudragit® S100 coating system across the physiological intestinal pH range.

Table 13: Stability studies.

Stability data (F013)										
Pack	HDPE bottle 120cc/38mm, 60's count, 3.0g Desiccant						40°C/75%RH			
Description			Red-brown colored capsule shaped tablet without imprinting							
Time point			Initial		1M		2M		3M	
Assay			100.30%		100.40%		98.50%		99.70%	
Dissolution	Time in min	Limit	% Drug release	%RSD	%Drug release	%RSD	% Drug release	%RSD	% Drug release	%RSD
0.1N HCl	2Hrs	NMT1.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
pH 6 phosphate buffer	1Hrs	NMT1.0	0	0	0	0	0.2	20.4	0.1	40.8
pH 7.2 phosphate buffer	15	NLT 85 in 90min	8.8	12.2	9.2	15.8	7.8	14.5	6.8	15.2
	30		51.6	7.5	52.0	7.2	50.6	10.2	49.6	6.8
	45		86.6	6.3	87.5	6.0	85.6	5.4	84.6	4.5
	60		96.1	1.0	97.2	1.5	94.9	1.2	95.9	1.5
	75		100.1	0.8	99.8	0.7	98.9	0.8	98.5	1.0
	90		100.8	0.8	100.2	0.6	100.5	0.6	99.9	0.6
Water content			3.2		3.2		3.3		4.1	
Related substances			RRT		%Impurity		%Impurity		%Impurity	
2,5-Dihydroxy benzoic acid			0		0		0		0	
4- Amino salicylic acid			0		0		0		0	
3- Amino salicylic acid			0		0		0		0	
3- Amino benzoic acid			0		0		0		0	
Unknown			0		0		0		0	
% of total impurity			0		0		0		0	

OBSERVATION

Accelerated stability studies conducted at 40°C/75% RH for three months demonstrated that the optimized formulation remained physically, chemically, and functionally stable throughout the study period. Assay values remained within 98.5–100.4%, while dissolution performance showed no significant change compared with the initial profile. Water content increased only marginally from 3.2% to 4.1%, indicating adequate

moisture protection provided by the HDPE bottle and desiccant system. No known or unknown degradation products were detected during storage, confirming the stability of Mesalamine and the effectiveness of the selected packaging configuration.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Significance of Core Formulation Optimization

Mesalamine is a high-dose drug with inherently poor flow and compressibility characteristics, making formulation development particularly challenging. The use of wet granulation was therefore selected to improve granule density, flowability, and content uniformity while ensuring adequate tablet mechanical strength. Comparison of the test core formulations with coat-removed reference tablets provided a direct understanding of the contribution of the core formulation to overall drug release behavior.

Among the eight formulations evaluated, F08 demonstrated the highest similarity to the coat-removed reference tablet, with an f_2 value of 80.4. The optimized combination of lactose monohydrate, Povidone K30, and sodium starch glycolate provided a balance between granule integrity and rapid hydration. Lower binder levels resulted in faster drug release, whereas excessive binder concentration delayed dissolution. Similarly, variations in sodium starch glycolate significantly affected water uptake and disintegration behavior. The results suggest that the release characteristics of the Mesalamine core are highly dependent on the balance between binder concentration and disintegrant efficiency.

The coat-removal approach proved particularly valuable because it allowed differentiation between the contribution of the tablet core and the enteric coating to the overall dissolution profile. This strategy enabled selection of a core formulation that closely mimicked the intrinsic release characteristics of the reference product before coating optimization was undertaken.

5.2 Effect of Coating Build-Up on Delayed-Release Performance

The enteric coating plays a critical role in determining the site and rate of Mesalamine release. Comparative dissolution studies of formulations F09–F13 clearly demonstrated that coating build-up had a significant influence on drug release kinetics.

Formulations containing higher coating levels (F09 and F10) exhibited delayed release compared with the reference product. The increased film thickness created a longer diffusion pathway for dissolution media and required additional time for polymer hydration and dissolution. Conversely, formulation F12, containing a 5.0% coating build-up, showed more rapid drug release, indicating that the coating thickness was insufficient to maintain the desired lag time.

Among the formulations investigated, F013 containing a 6.5% coating build-up produced a dissolution profile most comparable to the reference product, achieving an f_2 value of 75.1. This coating level provided sufficient protection during gastric and intestinal transit while allowing rapid release under colonic pH conditions. These findings highlight the narrow design space

associated with Mesalamine delayed-release products, where relatively small changes in coating thickness can substantially alter product performance.

5.3 Influence of Enteric Polymer Ionization on Drug Release

The dissolution behavior observed across pH 6.5–7.5 can be explained by the progressive ionization of methacrylic acid groups within the Eudragit polymer matrix. At lower pH values, limited ionization restricts polymer solubility and media penetration, thereby maintaining film integrity and delaying drug release. As pH increases, ionization of the carboxylic acid groups enhances polymer hydration and dissolution, leading to rapid disintegration of the coating film and subsequent drug release. The selected Eudragit® S100/Eudragit® L100 ratio successfully produced a controlled transition from enteric protection to rapid release, closely reproducing the release characteristics of the reference product.

5.4 Relevance to Generic Development of Mesalamine Delayed-Release Products

Development of generic Mesalamine delayed-release products remains challenging due to the drug's local mechanism of action and high intrinsic variability. Unlike systemically acting drugs, therapeutic performance depends primarily on achieving the correct site of release rather than maximizing systemic exposure. Consequently, small variations in formulation composition, coating thickness, or manufacturing parameters can significantly influence product performance.

The present study demonstrates a systematic development strategy involving core optimization, coat-removed reference comparison, and coating optimization to address these challenges. The optimized formulation successfully met USP delayed-release requirements, achieved dissolution similarity to the reference product, and remained stable under accelerated storage conditions.

Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of understanding polymer functionality and coating process variables during development of pH-dependent colon-targeted drug delivery systems. The findings provide a practical framework for future development of generic Mesalamine delayed-release formulations and other locally acting gastrointestinal drug products requiring precise site-specific delivery.

8. CONCLUSION

A systematic formulation development strategy was successfully employed for the development of a colon-targeted delayed-release Mesalamine tablet. Evaluation of coat-removed reference tablets enabled identification of a core formulation exhibiting dissolution behavior comparable to the intrinsic release characteristics of the reference product. Among the investigated formulations,

F08 demonstrated the highest similarity to the reference core and was selected for coating optimization studies.

Optimization of the dual-polymer enteric coating system comprising Eudragit® S100 and Eudragit® L100 demonstrated that coating build-up plays a critical role in controlling delayed-release performance. The optimized formulation F013 containing a 6.5% coating build-up exhibited dissolution characteristics most similar to those of the reference product under USP dissolution conditions.

Additional discriminatory dissolution studies performed across multiple physiologically relevant pH conditions further confirmed the robustness of the formulation and highlighted the influence of polymer ionization behavior on release kinetics. Accelerated stability studies demonstrated maintenance of assay, dissolution performance, moisture content, and impurity profile throughout storage.

Overall, the study demonstrates that successful development of delayed-release Mesalamine tablets requires careful optimization of both core composition and enteric coating characteristics. The development strategy described herein provides a practical and scientifically justified framework for the development of generic colon-targeted delayed-release drug products.

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